

Abstract

Synthetic neurocomputers consist of evolutionarily designed devices—living biological neurons cultured *in vitro*—and conventional in-silico computing, integrated into an engineered architecture. This forms a unique computational structure for achieving scientific progress. This position paper provides a concise overview of the field’s current state, potential opportunities, and strategic directions for future research and development. Key research challenges include advancing culturing and biofabrication techniques, engineering improved biological-silicon interface techniques, and broadly exploring architectural and algorithmic principles. We recommend increasing engagement through open-access and remote-access pathways, and maintaining interdisciplinary collaboration with an emphasis on symbiotic research. We propose that neurocomputers will continue to mature through modular engineering principles, coupled with data-sharing and careful testing, with a particular focus on reliability. Meanwhile, bioethics and social reception should be emphasized as neurocomputers move towards broader commercialization. Neurocomputers should target wide-ranging markets while generating interest in academia, government, and industry. The complex dynamical processes in biological neurons endow synthetic neurocomputers with the potential to tackle a wide range of scientific questions requiring sophisticated information processing, while also providing valuable insights for future computational technologies. Synthetic neurocomputers are poised to drive scientific research and computational technology with their interdisciplinary applications and innovative capabilities, holding great promise for advancing our understanding of biological, computational, and general sciences.

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Synthetic Neurocomputers: Advancing Scientific Research through Computing with Living Neurons

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1. Introduction

Synthetic neurocomputers leverage modern engineering progress and evolutionary design through an *in vitro* neural computing system. This unique interface between biological and silicon computing opens the door to novel scientific advancements.

Analog computing, tracing back to Vannevar Bush’s differential analyzer, has historically relied on linear computing components. However, the introduction of nonlinear dynamics—which is naturally implemented in neurobiology with remarkable energy efficiency—can significantly enhance computational capabilities in support of scientific discoveries and solving complex problems in dynamical systems. Additionally, biological neural networks offer collocated processing and memory, parallel processing capabilities, and robustness to damage and noise, making them an untapped resource for advanced information processing. They can not only mitigate noise concerns, a burden of analog computing, but also leverage it to their advantage¹, enabling them to perform complex computations under noisy conditions with high accuracy.

Neurocomputers are designed using living neurons that can be cultured *in vitro* through various methods, including dissociated primary neuron cultures²⁻⁴, organotypic brain slices⁴, stem-cell derived neurons³⁻⁵, and brain organoids^{5,6}. Neural networks can be stimulated chemically, optogenetically, electrophysiologically, or mechanically, and their activity measured using electrophysiology or microscopy. These cultures can be engineered into structured 2D²⁻⁴ and 3D networks with diverse topologies (e.g., rods, cubes, toroids, spheroids) leveraging modern biofabrication techniques⁷. These systems can include various neuronal cell types and glial cells, such as astrocytes, at different concentrations and locations.

Computationally, synthetic neurocomputers have evolved from performing simple logical operations² to playing pong³, performing speech recognition, and predicting nonlinear equations⁶, albeit with limited performance. Yet, even at their nascent design stage, neurocomputers have been shown to outperform conventional state-of-the-art (SOTA) AI in terms of sample efficiency⁸. This is particularly notable given that the brain is predicted to be over five orders of magnitude more power efficient than conventional AI hardware running a comparable neural network⁶. These systems are now versatile, open-source⁴, and remotely accessible⁵, but there is considerable room for growth.

2. Potential Contributions

Expanding on these foundational developments and the versatile applications of synthetic neurocomputers, a myriad of potential contributions can further revolutionize scientific research and computational technologies.

These systems can be modularized and scaled into functional building blocks to improve engineering design. Techniques exist to selectively route information from different units using macroscopic or microscopic structures, in addition to dynamically altering activity patterns through neurons’ inherent plasticity, either through selective stimulation or innate reorganization⁹. Individual components should be defined and characterized to allow for more complex system design. For example, structural mapping using connectomics¹⁰ and microscopy^{3,11} can provide better analysis methods. With efforts in scaling and modularization^{4,5} across hardware, software, and wetware (i.e., biological components), the barrier to entry will continue to decrease and more researchers will be able to remotely or directly access these systems.

It is important to establish benchmarks for neurocomputers. These standards can include cognitive tests such as the Go/No-Go and N-back tasks, as well as standard computational benchmarks like MNIST for computer vision and GLUE for natural language processing. Additionally, tests akin to SPEC benchmarks could be developed for evaluating general-purpose computing performance.

Integrating neurocomputers into existing brain-on-a-chip research¹² is crucial and has already begun^{3,13,14}, as both fields can benefit significantly from this consolidation. In the future, adjusting various conditions while performing learning and computational tasks can break new ground in understanding and addressing cognitive disease states or enhancements. Conversely, the customization of culturing (e.g., cell concentrations) and interfacing techniques (e.g., flexible 3D micro-electrode arrays), combined with improved architectural principles (e.g., multi-scale designs) and advanced analysis techniques (e.g., information flow),

promises to unlock new computational capabilities. This further allows for unparalleled control and precision in addressing neuroscientific questions. These synergistic advancements will mutually enhance both fields, driving progress in understanding and utilizing neurocomputers.

Computation can be performed through reservoir computing⁶ or other innovative paradigms. Higher-order programming considerations, such as languages (e.g., assembly calculus¹⁵) and compilers, should be developed and tested, while efforts to understand theoretical constraints, guarantees, and limitations are undertaken concurrently. These insights can also be applied to other neural architectures and computational technologies. Neurocomputers may even provide a pathway to artificial general intelligence (AGI).

Concerted efforts should be made to advance culturing and biofabrication techniques for ease, longevity, and capacity; to engineer more affordable, high-density, and flexible stimulation and recording¹⁶ techniques in a low-power, online setting; and to broadly explore architectural and algorithmic principles.

3. Strategic Directions

Beyond any individual contribution, it is crucial to strategically guide the field's development to ensure broad impact and sustainable growth.

Interdisciplinary collaboration—focusing on symbiotic research and development—should be central, as neurocomputers, like conventional computers, require the wide-ranging expertise of individuals (e.g., neuroscientists, computer scientists, materials scientists) while providing cross-domain benefits. Emphasis should be placed upon developing general open-source techniques and broader remote-access pathways, coupled with improved user interfaces, to expand the pool of researchers advancing the field. Outreach and educational opportunities should be implemented to engage and inform a wider audience and future workforce.

Maturation of synthetic neurocomputers will occur as they continue to be scaled through modular engineering principles. System longevity, reliability, and self-sustainability should remain major foci to expand potential use cases. Rigorous testing of theories, models, and technologies is needed to establish the validity and reliability of neurocomputers. Open data and resource sharing should be prioritized to facilitate this process. As the field matures, interdisciplinary work should continue but also transform to allow for specialization within sub-domains to accelerate future progress.

Given the unique considerations of working with living biological materials, a strong focus on bioethics and social reception should be maintained to ensure safe and responsible development.

In the long term, broader commercialization of more developed and sustainable systems will help reduce costs and advance the field. This should include identifying potential markets and applications for neurocomputers (e.g., neuroscience research, brain machine interfaces, scientific computing) under regulatory compliance and limitations. Moreover, forming strategic partnerships within industry and governmental agencies will aid in accelerating the development of neurocomputers.

4. Conclusion

Key challenges and opportunities in the field of synthetic neurocomputing have been highlighted, with a particular focus on their application in scientific research. By leveraging the complex dynamical processes inherent in biological neurons, synthetic neurocomputers have the potential to tackle a wide range of scientific questions that require sophisticated information processing. Additionally, these systems can provide valuable insights and inspiration for developing future computational technologies.

The promise of synthetic neurocomputers in advancing scientific research is immense, offering new tools and methodologies to further our understanding of the biological, computational, and general sciences.

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